

Evaluation of chemical control of weeds associated with caraway cultivation (*Carum carvi* L., var. *Aprim*) and its effect on some plant growth and development parameters

Hodnocení možností chemické regulace plevelů v porostech kmínu (*Carum carvi* L., var. *Aprim*) a dopadů testovaných herbicidů na růstové a vývojové parametry plodiny

Muñoz Arbeález, M. – Seidenglanz, M.

Agritec Plant Research Ltd.

Abstract

Caraway (*Carum carvi* L.) is considered a minor crop in most countries, where it is cultivated, and it represents an important source of essential oil used for medicine, condiments, and lately, animal nutrition. Lack of information on the correct agricultural practices in caraway creates a difficulty for growers to manage adequately the crop. One of the major constraints is weed management, which results in difficulty due to the slow initial growth, the weak root system of the crop, and a low number of registered products against weeds. The main objective of this research was to evaluate different doses and application times of herbicides, on the population of weeds associated with the caraway crop and its effect on the growth and development of the crop. The field trial was conducted in the north-eastern part of the Czech Republic, Olomouc region during the Autumn of 2020 until the Summer of 2021, using the variety *Aprim* "winter caraway", which is characterized by a shortened vegetation period than the traditional biennial varieties. The treatments consisted of 12 herbicides, some of them registered in the Czech Republic. Weed density, weed biomass, and weeds diversity were measured during the growing period. Caraway biomass and the plant growth parameters as rootstock diameter, number of leaves, stage of development of flower primordia, and yield, were also recorded. The results showed that the use of the tested herbicides was effective in reducing the weed density. Pre-emergent treatments showed 40 % more effectiveness against the total weed density. No effects were found in weed diversity. The treatments with S-metolachlor+terbuthylazine presented negative effects on plant growth. With the exception of one rate of S-metolachlor+terbuthylazine (5.0 l/ha), all other sprayed treatments presented higher yield than the control, although the increase was not confirmed as significant, it was noted that some of the treatments that had the more advanced stage of flower primordia were also the ones with better yields. These results confirms that it is possible to use chemical weed control in caraway cultivation without affecting plant growth.

Key words: winter caraway, herbicide effectiveness, yield, weeds

Abstrakt

Kmín kořenný (*Carum carvi* L.) je ve většině zemí, kde je pěstován, považován za plodinu minoritní. Přesto jsou jeho plody významným zdrojem esenciálních olejů využívaných v medicíně, potravinářství a poslední dobou i ve výživě zvířat. Nedostatek informací o vhodné technologii pěstování však způsobuje zejména nezkušeným pěstitelům značné potíže. Jednou z hlavních obtíží je regulace plevelů, což je způsobeno velmi

pomalým počátečním růstem kmínu a rozvojem jeho kořenového systému a též značně omezenými možnostmi při výběru registrovaných herbicidů. Hlavním cílem této studie bylo porovnat účinnost herbicidů aplikovaných v různých dávkách a termínech na běžné plevele v porostech kmínu a též vyhodnotit dopad testovaných aplikací na růst a vývoj plodiny. Hodnocení probíhala v polním maloparcelním pokusu vedeném na lokalitě Vikýřovice (Olomoucký kraj, okres Šumperk) od podzimu 2020 do léta 2021. Pracovalo se s odrůdou Aprim, která je charakteristická zkráceným obdobím růstu a vývoje oproti tradičním dvouletým formám kmínu. V pokusu bylo porovnáváno 12 herbicidních variant + kontrola. Některé z variant představují registrované přípravky. Hodnocení účinnosti na plevele byla zaměřena na tyto parametry: výskyt plevelů (pokryvnost), biomasa plevelů a jejich druhová diverzita. Dopad na plodinu byl hodnocen porovnáním těchto parametrů: biomasa kmínu, tloušťka kořenového krčku, počet listů na rostlině, stupeň vývoje květních primordií a výnos nažek z parcel. Preemergentní aplikace snížily úroveň zaplevelení (weed density, pokryvnost) o 40 % účinněji než aplikace postemergentní. Nebyl však zaznamenán vliv na druhovou diverzitu. Varianty s účinnou látkou S-metolachlor+terbuthylazine měly negativní dopad na růst kmínu. S výjimkou pro variantu, kde byl aplikován S-metolachlor+terbuthylazine (přípravek Gardoprim: 5 l/ha), byl ze všech ostatních herbicidy ošetřených variant získán vyšší parcelní výnos nažek než z neošetřené kontroly (rozdíl mezi kontrolou a ošetřenými variantami nebyl statisticky významný). Nejvýnosnější se ukázaly být varianty, u kterých byl v předjaří zaznamenán více pokročilý stupeň vývoje květních primordií. Výsledky ukazují, že možnosti pro bezpečnou a účinnou kontrolu plevelů pomocí herbicidů existují.

Klíčová slova: kmín se zkrácenou vegetační dobou, účinnost herbicidů, výnos, plevele

Introduction

Caraway (*Carum carvi*) is an aromatic plant belonging to the Apiaceae family, plants with high economic importance. It is widely used for condiments, medicine, and industrial purposes (Sayed *et al.*, 2017). Caraway can also be used as a feed additive in animal nutrition, where the addition of this plant has shown potential in the manipulation of rumen fermentation, improvement of animal productivity, and enhancing the quality of milk fatty acids profile (Rahmy *et al.*, 2019; Mahmoud *et al.*, 2020). Furthermore, caraway could be used as an alternative to control pain and inflammation in animals; recently it has shown some antidepressant properties that require further study (Seddighfar *et al.*, 2020; Es-safi *et al.*, 2021). Presently, the studies related to caraway, focus only on the medicinal, industrial, and culinary properties, leaving behind the agronomy of the crop.

Caraway is considered a minor crop in most countries and this fact has led to a lack of attention for the improvement of its cultivation. One of

the major constraints in caraway cultivation is the weed control. The plant has a weakly branched root system, hence, low competitive ability with other plants for water and nutrients (Geoffriau & Simon, 2020). This is important to manage during the period of crop emergence that is particularly slow in the caraway plants, to avoid nutrient competition (Malhotra, 2012), and further weed infestation on the fields. In addition to the threat of weeds at the beginning of the growing phase of the caraway, decreasing weed population to the minimum reduces the competition with the crop, and maintain quality at harvest, since it is difficult and cost increasing operation to separate the seed of weeds from caraway fruits after harvest, reducing its value (Malhotra, 2012).

The scarce information that is found related to caraway management, is focused on the traditional biennial and annual forms of caraway. Under natural conditions typical for central Europe, the two-year forms are sown at spring (April, May) and harvested next year in July / August, occupying

a field during two growing seasons. In addition to those forms, another caraway form is used in minor proportion, the "winter caraway" variety *Aprim* (Šmirous, 2016). The variety shows a substantially shortened period of cultivation than the biennial forms. So, the period of vegetation for *Aprim* is shorter than in the case of traditional varieties and similar to common winter crops such as winter oilseed rape or winter cereals which conveys practical advantage for growers. There is a very limited amount of information about weed control possibilities in the crop. The different time of sowing and emerging of this variety is a cause of the fact that weed control is carried out under different agroecological conditions in *Aprim* than in traditional two-year forms. The traditional two-year forms differ from crop originated from *Aprim* seed stock in the spectrum of weed species, in different rates of a plant emerging and growing at early phases (especially when September and October are characteristic with cold weather) and in the lower ability of caraway plants to compete with weeds.

Currently, weed management in the Czech Republic is through chemical herbicides, however, the number of protection products registered for medicinal, spicy, and aromatic crops is low, which makes it important to find the most suitable products for weed control on caraway crops and the right time of application. Pre-emergent herbicides have been proved effective against weeds. However, the use of these products can present phytotoxic effects on the main crop, primarily on the inhibition of emergence or on the newly emerging plants (Vaculík, 2014). Post-emergence herbicides can also be used to control weeds on caraway crops but it can be more complicated against dicotyledon weeds due to product selectivity (Vaculík, 2020), and due to the fact of the slower emerging rate of caraway in comparison with the main dicotyledon weeds, which usually accompany caraway plants.

The main objective of this research was to evaluate different doses and application times of herbicides, on the population of weeds associated with

the caraway crop and its effect on the growth and development of the crop.

Materials and methods

Experimental design

The experiment was carried out in the north-eastern part of the Czech Republic, Olomouc region, near the town of Šumperk at the locality of Vikýřovice, with an altitude of 335 meters above sea level (coordinates: 49.9652603N, 17.0147031E). Meteorological data were obtained from the meteorological station located in the area, long-term average (2014–2019), and the date from the period of this experiment (2020–2021) are shown in Figure 1.

The trial was established using the caraway variety *Aprim*, which presents a shorter vegetation period compared to the traditional two years varieties. The experimental field was ploughed after harvest of the previous crop (spring barley – commercial crop, half of August), and the caraway was sown in September 2020, at a rate of 15 g of seeds 10 m⁻². Ten days before sowing, the plots were fertilized with Urea and NPK at a rate of 100 kg ha⁻¹ each, to increase the C:N ratio and stimulate the mineralization of the straw from the previously grown crop barley.

The experiment was established as a completely randomized block design with four repetitions. In total, there were 13 treatments corresponding to 12 herbicide treatments and control without herbicide application (Table 1). Thus, 52 plots were established, each with an area of 12.5 m² (1.25 m × 10 m). Buffer rows were left at the border of each repetition.

Tested herbicides and application

Table 1 shows the herbicides and application rates used in each treatment during the trial. The used herbicides are recommended for the control of dicotyledon weeds and some of them also monocotyledons. Aclonifen (Bandur), MCPB (Butoxone), and tembotrione+ isoxadifen-ethyl (Laudis) are registered in Czech Republic for use in caraway crops and they were tested in the recommended dose. The other herbicides, pendimethalin (Stomp

AQUA), S-metolachlor+terbuthylazine (Gardoprim Plus Gold 500 SC), and isoxaflutole (Merlin 750 WG) were tested at different doses. The pre-emergent application was made with a HEGE sprayer, seven days after sowing (DAS), and for the post-emergent application (45 DAS), a dorsal sprayer was used. Because the previous crop was a cereal, it was decided to realize a uniform application of herbicide for the control of monocotyledon weeds, 52 DAS in all plots using Quizalofop-P-ethyl at a rate of 1 l ha⁻¹ of the herbicide.

Data collection and analyses

Weeds

Density and biomass

To calculate the weed density, all the weed individuals inside a quadrat of 0.2 m² were counted

Equation 2: Abbott's formula to test effectiveness

$$\% \text{ Effectiveness} = 1 - \left(\frac{\text{Number of weed individuals after the treatment}}{\text{Number of weed individuals in control}} \right) \times 100$$

Weed diversity

The diversity of the weeds was evaluated using the Simpson index of diversity (Simpson, 1949) in all treatments through Equation 1.

Equation 1: Simpson's Diversity Index

$$D = 1 - \frac{\sum n(n-1)}{\sum N(N-1)}$$

n = number of individuals of each species

N = total number of individuals of all species

Caraway

Biomass

Crop biomass was assessed at 63 and 217 days after sowing as described for weed biomass. All caraway plants with roots were collected inside three 0.20 m² quadrat in each plot. The plants were dried three hours at a constant temperature of 108 °C and the weight was recorded for analysis.

Plant growth parameters

three times during the trial at 40,62 and 206 days after sowing (DAS). Each count was made in five randomly laid quadrat within each plot and all dicotyledon weeds were identified to species level. Weed biomass was measured 63 DAS, all weed individuals inside a quadrat of 0.2 m² were collected with their root system. Three such quadrats were taken in each plot, dried three hours at 108 °C, and weighted.

Herbicide effectiveness

The effectiveness of the herbicides was evaluated according to the protocols of the European and Mediterranean Plant Protection Organization (EPPO). Abbotts Formula (Abbott, 1925) was used for the calculations (Equation 2).

After the winter season (181 DAS, beginning of March), ten caraway plants were randomly sampled in each plot with their root system. For each plant, the number of leaves, rootstock diameter (RSD), and stage of development of flower primordia were measured.

For the determination of the stage of the flower primordia on the caraway plants, a pre-sampling was made on the field, then observing and classifying the development into five stages (0–4) based on Procházka & Vrzalová (1988).

Yield

Close to crop maturity the percentage of flowering plants in each plot was measured visually. The harvest of the caraway was made with a small plot harvester Wintersteiger Quantum and the harvest was made separately in each plot. The purity of the seed was determined to calculate the real yield for every plot.

Statistical analyses

The data from the trial was statistically evaluated through one-way analysis of variance and Tukey test for the case of caraway, weed biomass, and herbicide effectiveness as the data followed the normality and homoscedasticity assumptions. Kruskal-Wallis was used for weed density, weed diversity, stage of flower primordia, and yield, as the data did not follow the assumptions even when transformed. The differences between individual means were considered significant at $p < 0.05$. The Statistica TIBCO Software version 13.5 was used to perform the analyses. Correlations between the plant growth parameters and weed parameters were determined using Pearson's correlations.

Results and discussion

Weeds

Density and biomass

The weed density in the plots treated with pre-emergent herbicides was lower than control plots 40 DAS. The plots corresponding to post-emergent herbicides application did not differ from control; at this point, no post-emergent herbicides had been applied (Figure 2).

Two weeks after the application of the post-emergent herbicides (62 DAS), the weed density differed between the pre and post-emergent herbicides. Weed density on the pre-emergent treatments was lower than the post-emergent treatments and the control (Figure 2).

After the winter (206 DAS), no difference in the level of weed density between the control and the plots treated with post-emergent herbicides was observed. However, the treatments with pre-emergent herbicides and Temb (post-emergent) did not present any significant difference; same as the treatments Pend2.6, Pend3.0, Pend3.5, Isox0.08 and the post-emergent PendPos (Figure 2).

No significant differences were detected in weed biomass. Although, weed density was higher in the post emergent treatments, the weed species were variable, and this could have influenced the biomass (Figure 3).

Herbicide effectiveness

The effectiveness of the herbicides was calculated for every treatment, 206 DAS according to Equation 1. The effectiveness of applied herbicides on the most common species, *Lamium purpureum*, *Veronica persica*, and *Viola arvensis* was also calculated (Table 2).

Compared with control, the herbicide effectiveness on the most frequent weed species encountered on the field trial (*Lamium purpureum*, *Veronica persica*, and *Viola arvensis*) was significantly higher in all the pre-emergent treatments except Pend2.6 (Pendimethalin at rate 2.6 l/h⁻¹). On the other hand, post-emergent herbicides did not have an effect against the most frequent weeds found in this trial (except for Tembotrione, in *Lamium purpureum*). According to the labels, all the pre-emergent herbicides used in the present study (except Isoxaflutole-Merlin 750 WG) include *Lamium purpureum*, *Veronica persica*, and *Viola arvensis* in the spectrum of their efficiency, listing them as a "sensitive weed" (Agromanuál.cz, n.d.). Pendimethalin, as a post-emergent herbicide was not sufficiently effective against the weeds specified above, even though it is labeled against it, which could be explained by the inadequate time of application; it is recommended to apply the post-emergent herbicide when the weeds have maximum two true leaves, which was not the case for these species. *Lamium purpureum*, *Veronica persica*, and *Viola arvensis* are not labelled as a target in MCPB-Butoxone, and Tembotrione-Laudis only has *Lamium purpureum* as a sensitive weed, thus the result concurs with the labels.

Another factor that could have influenced the effectiveness of the herbicides in the mentioned species, was the form of application. Opposed to the application of the pre-emergent herbicides, that was made by the HEGE sprayer, the post-emergent herbicides were applied manually with a dorsal sprayer (self-propelled sprayer HEGE was not possible to use due to its high weight – at the time of the application the soil was too wet), this could result in non-homogeneous spray in the plots, resulting in lower effectiveness.

Nevertheless, according to the growers in the area, the most problematic weeds in the cultivation of the caraway are dicotyledons plants, especially the Chamomille group (*Tripleurospermum inodorum*, *Matricaria chamomilla*, *Anthemis arvensis*) and *Cirsium arvense*; although they were not identified in this study, it warrants future studies from different areas and extended to more growing seasons to optimize herbicide utilization in caraway under more scenarios.

For the total weed density, the pre-emergent treatments had approximately 40 % more effective against the weeds, however, the difference among them was not statistically significant (Table 2).

Weed diversity

None of the studied treatments had effects on species diversity, which can be seen as a positive effect on the ecosystem. Diversified weed communities can promote ecosystem services, by limiting the effect of the most competitive and dominant species on the crop (Adeux *et al.*, 2019, Guerra *et al.*, 2022).

Caraway

Biomass

In autumn (63 DAS), the biomass of the caraway did not differ among the treatments, including control, possibly for the slow initial growth of the plant. After winter (217 DAS), the biomass of the caraway was lower in Met5.0 compared with control, Pend3.5, Met2.0, Isox0.08, and all the post-emergent treatments (Figure 4). Met5.0 and Met3.5 presented the lowest mean value overall. This can result in the reduction of the number of branches and lateral shoots, the number of umbels per plant, or the seed size, influencing the final yield of the crop (Seidler-Łożykowska & Bocianowski, 2012).

In general, no significant correlation was found between the caraway biomass, weed biomass, and seed yield.

Plant growth parameters

181 DAS (shortly after winter, beginning of March) a significant and positive correlation was found between the RSD and the stage of development of the flower primordia ($r = 0.431$), the same

as for the number of leaves and the stage of flower primordia ($r = 0.502$). There was no significant correlation between the number of leaves and the RSD. That applies to all treatments assessed as one group regardless of the herbicide used.

Although the number of leaves and the rootstock diameter did not present a significant correlation, it is confirmed by other studies that the flowering stage is characterized by the diameter of the rootstock and number of leaves (Németh *et al.*, 1997). The rootstock diameter and its positive correlation with the stage of flower primordia could mean that the plants with a more advanced stage of development, would have more success on the flowering phase and thus the crop development, which translates to a higher probability of better yield.

In the caraway, the plant size plays an important role in the development of flowers and the capacity of plants to create more and larger flowers, which are the target parts for crop cultivation. For the biennial form of caraway, a minimum rootstock diameter of 5mm at the end of the first vegetation year is a precondition for generative differentiation in the second year (Németh *et al.*, 1997), however, for the form of caraway with a shortened period of vegetation (variety *Aprim*) used in this study, the rootstock diameter on the control was 3.2 mm shortly after winter and it presented generative differentiation. In the present, no specific studies are found for caraway var., *Aprim* to determine what are the parameters for generative differentiation, suggesting that more studies focused on this variety are needed.

Some significant differences among the treatments on the number of leaves, rootstock diameter, and stage of flower primordia were recorded. The RSD was lower in the pre-emergent treatments with Pendimethalin and S-metolachlor+terbuthylazine at all rates, when compared with control. The highest values were found in Acl, Isox0.13, and the post-emergent PendPos, MCPB3.0, and Temb2.25. For the case of the number of leaves per plant, the results were variable, ranking from 3.8 leaves/plant (Acl) to 7.25 leaves/plant (Isox0.08) also having lower values on pre-emergent treatments. The stage

of the flower primordia was also affected by the different treatments, the stage was lower on the Pend3.5, Met2.0, and Met5.0 treatments. compared with control. The post-emergent treatments presented plants with a higher flower development stage in general (Figure 5). For the biennial form of caraway, it has been studied that vernalization is not the main factor that controls floral development (Samuoliene *et al.*, 2009), hence it is possible that the stage of flower development, in the case of winter caraway (variety *Aprim*) in this study was affected not by the temperature, but for the herbicides used.

According to the herbicides classification, S-metolachlor affects cellular metabolism and terbuthylazine inhibits photosynthesis (HRAC, 2021). Which could affect the caraway growth and be a sign of non-selectivity of these active ingredients on this crop. All rates of the mentioned herbicides affected the RSD which is positively correlated with the stage of flower primordia, that, although the difference was not statistically significant in the other rates (Pend2.6, Pend3.0, Met3.5) with the control, it is clear that presented lower stage of development of flower primordia and also indicating that higher rates, could have more negative effects on the caraway growth (Figure 5).

These results can be used in the next studies of this form of caraway to also understand the plant development and the factors affecting flowering initiation.

Field observations

During the first assessment (40 DAS) it was observed that some of the plants in the plots treated with S-metolachlor+terbuthylazine at 3.5 and 5 l/ha showed some symptoms of curling of the leaves. In the second assessment (62 DAS), it was recorded that the plants were relatively smaller in some plots treated with S-metolachlor+terbuthylazine at 3.5 and 5 l/ha and in plots treated with Pendimethalin at 3.0 l/ha.

A third observation was made 105 DAS detect phytotoxicity of the applied herbicides and it was recorded that the plants treated with S-metolachlor+terbuthylazine at 3.5 and 5 l/ha pre-

sented some degree of yellowing, leaf curling and were stunted compared to the plants of the other treatments. The plots treated with Pendimethalin at 3.0 l/ha were slightly stunted compared to the control. Some of these observations can be seen in Figure 6.

The plots treated with S-metolachlor+terbuthylazine at 3.5 and 5 l/ha showed some degree of phytotoxicity on the caraway plants and lower biomass compared with the other treatments. These results concur partially with other trials on caraway where the herbicides S-metolachlor+terbuthylazine and Isoxaflutole showed problems with selectiveness with caraway plants in the retardation of emergency and partial absence of emerging plants and after an emergency (Vaculík, 2014). Despite that, in this trial Isoxaflutole did not affect the caraway plants, on the opposite, the plots treated with Isoxaflutole 0.08 were the ones with the highest biomass and high effectiveness.

Yield parameters

Close to maturity, the percentage of flowering plants was recorded in all the plots; the pre-emergent treatments Met3.5 and Met 5.0 presented a lower percentage of flowering plants compared to control and the other treatments. This agrees with the previous assessments in plant growth parameters, where the same treatments, presented the lowest development rates.

The final yield (t/ha) did not present statistical differences between treatments and control, possibly due to the high variability of it and a limited number of samples per treatment (n per treatment = 4). Nevertheless, all the treatments except Met5.0 had higher seed yields than control, concurring with the previous results. The plots with the pre-emergent treatments Pendimethalin at 3.5, Isoxaflutole 0.08, and post-emergent MCPB 3.0 presented the highest yields (Figure 7). In a similar trial in caraway, the untreated control resulted in a yield of only about one-third compared to the plants treated with pre-emergent herbicides (Vaculík, 2014).

Currently, only Aclonifen (Bandur), MCPB (Butoxone 400), and Tembotrione (Laudis) are reg-

istered herbicides against dicotyledons weeds in the Czech Republic for the use on caraway crops, and their effectiveness against weeds was confirmed in the present study. From the unregistered products, S-metolachlor+terbuthylazine (Gardorprim Plus Gold SC) was effective but also showed symptoms of phytotoxicity, reflected on biomass and low yield. Pendimethalin (Stomp AQUA) was effective as pre-emergent and post-emergent and the caraway biomass was affected by neither type of application. Isoxaflutole (Merlin 750 WG) at a rate of 0.13 kg/ha was also effective against weeds, and caraway plants in these plots produced the highest biomass and stage of flower primordia of all treatments.

Conclusions

This study proved that is possible the use different herbicide treatments for the control of weed

in caraway crops. However, some herbicides can negatively affect crop growth and their ability to produce generative organs (umbels, fruits, seeds). It concerns especially two higher rates of S-metolachlor+terbuthylazine. The other tested herbicides may be recommended for the control of weeds in the caraway crop and when they are applied at a sufficient level of weed infestation, is it possible to expect they will prevent the crop from yield decreasing.

Rates of the selected herbicides should depend on the abundance of weeds on the crop and future studies should focus on interactions of caraway with specific weeds under a wider range of climatic conditions and management practices, and on determining the levels of weed infestation for which the real necessity to control weeds with a herbicide exists to prevent a significant decrease in yield quantity and quality.

Tab. 1 Herbicides and application rates used in each treatment during the trial

Treatment	Active Ingredient	Mode of Action	Application Rate	Type of application and Date of Spraying
Acl	Aclonifen	Inhibition of Solanesyl Diphosphate Synthase	3 l/ha	Pre-emergent
Pend2.6	Pendimethalin	Inhibition of Microtubule Assembly	2.6 l/ha	Pre-emergent
Pend3.0			3.0 l/ha	
Pend3.5			3.5 l/ha	
Met2.0	S-metolachlor, terbuthylazine	Inhibition of Very Long-Chain Fatty Acid Synthesis	2.0 l/ha	Pre-emergent
Met3.5			3.5 l/ha	
Met5.0			D1 Serine 264 binders	
Isox0.08	Isoxaflutole	Inhibition of Hydroxyphenyl Pyruvate Dioxygenase	0.08 kg/ha	Pre-emergent
Isox0.13			0.13 kg/ha	
PendPos	Pendimethalin	Inhibition of Microtubule Assembly	3.0 l/ha	Post-emergent
MCPB3.0	MCPB	Auxin Mimics	3 l/ha	Post-emergent
Temb	Tembotrione, isoxadifen-ethyl	Inhibition of Hydroxyphenyl Pyruvate Dioxygenase	2.25 l/ha	Post-emergent

DAS: days after sowing

Tab. 2 Herbicide effectiveness using Abbott's equation 206 DAS

Treatment	% Effectiveness				
	Total weeds	<i>Viola arvensis</i>	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	<i>Veronica persica</i>	
Acl	90.2 (±0) *	100(±0) *	100(±0) *	100(±0) *	
Pend2.6	75.6(±5.7) *	64.7(±10.2) n. s	92.3(±6.25) n. s	71.4(±28.9) n. s	
Pend3.0	95.1(±3.8) *	100(±16.6) *	100(±0) *	71.4(±0) *	
Pend3.5	90.2(±5.3) *	94.1(±6.25) *	100(±0) *	100(±0) *	
Pre-emergent	Met2.0	97.5(±1.9) *	94.1(±5) *	100(±0) *	100(±0) *
	Met3.5	100(±0) *	100(±0) *	100(±0) *	100(±0) *
	Met5.0	100(±0) *	100(±0) *	100(±0) *	100(±0) *
	Isox0.08	92.7(±9.4) *	100(±0) *	100(±0) *	100(±0) *
	Isox0.13	100(±0) *	100(±0) *	100(±0) *	100(±0) *
Post-emergent	PendPos	51.2(±10.3) *	5.9(±45.3) n. s	84.6(±7.2) n. s	100(±0) *
	MCPB3.0	48.7(±10.6) *	41.2(±21.6) n. s	46.2(±70.) n. s	42.9(±20.8) n. s
	Temb	58.5(±12.1) *	52.9(±12.1) n. s	100(±0) *	14.2(±88.6) n. s

*p < 0.05 n.s. not significant

Aclonifen, MCPB and tembotrione + isoxadifen-ethyl are the only herbicides, which are registered for use in caraway in the Czech Republic aimed at dicotyledon weeds

Fig. 1

Average monthly temperatures and precipitations on the study site in the growing season 2020–2021 and the long-term means (2014–2019)

Fig. 2
Weed density

Mean \pm standard deviation of the mean. DAS: days after sowing. The same letter in the same color indicates no difference between the treatments on the corresponding date.

Fig. 3
Weeds Biomass expressed in kg/m²

Measured 63 days after sowing. Same letter indicates no difference between the treatments.

Fig. 4
Caraway Biomass expressed
in kg/m²

Mean ± standard deviation of the mean. DAS: days after sowing. Same letter in the same color indicates no difference between the treatments on the corresponding date.

Fig. 5
Stage of development of
Flower Primordia at 181 days
after sowing

Mean ± standard deviation of the mean. Same letter indicates no significant difference.

Fig. 6
Observations on the plots
105 DAS

a. Control, b. Pend3.0, c. Isox0.13 vs Met 3.5, d. MCPB3.0 vs **Met5.0**

Fig. 7
Caraway yield (ton/ha)

Mean ± standard deviation of the mean. Same letter indicates no significant difference.

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Contact address

Ing. María Muñoz Arbeález, MSc.
Agritec Plant Research Ltd., Plant Protection Department
Zemědělská 2520/16, 787 01 Šumperk
E-mail: munoz@agritec.cz